
Impact of Self Esteem and Social Support on Examination Anxiety Among Medical and Law Students in Godfrey Okoye University.

Aigbiremhon, Ikekhide Joseph, Ph.D. and Ogbonna, Deborah Febechukwu

Department of Sociology/Psychology, Godfrey Okoye University,

Ugwuomu-Nike, Enugu State. Nigeria

Correspondence: aigbiremhon@gouni.edu.ng

Abstract

This study examined the influence of self-esteem and social support on examination anxiety among medical and law students in Enugu State. Guided by the Self-Determination Theory, Sociometer Theory, Attachment Theory, Buffering Hypothesis, Cognitive Appraisal Theory, and the Yerkes-Dodson Law, the research employed a correlational survey design involving 120 undergraduate students. Data were collected using standardized instruments: the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale, the Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS), and the Westside Test Anxiety Scale (WTAS). Results revealed that negative self-esteem was positively associated with higher examination anxiety, while positive self-esteem and family support significantly reduced anxiety levels. Age and gender also emerged as significant demographic predictors. The hierarchical regression model explained 34% of the variance in examination anxiety, with self-esteem being the strongest predictor. These findings highlight the importance of targeted interventions that strengthen students' self-worth and family-based support systems in order to mitigate anxiety in high-pressure academic environments.

Keywords: Self Esteem, Social Support and Test Anxiety.

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Introduction

Examinations are an essential part of academic assessment, often determining a change in level or as an indicator of academic intelligence, yet they often evoke significant rates of anxiety among university students, especially those in intense pressure fields such as the medical sciences and law. One of the most common anxiety types shown to be present among students, is examination anxiety. Examination anxiety is explained as a form of performance anxiety that is marked by high levels of worry, immense fear of failure and can even accompany physical symptoms such as inability to focus, rapid heartbeat, excessive sweating and in extreme cases, panic attacks. It involves the physical stress that individuals go through when they are faced with a situation where they are measured during examinations or assessments. When severe, it can impede on levels of academic performance and overall psychological well-being. It is a prevalent and pervasive problem amongst many undergraduates as they try to navigate the tumultuous demands of higher education. The recent comprehensive and competitive nature of the school environment has intensified the pressure that students face to achieve high grades, prevent failure and secure future opportunities (Karim & Lachmi, 2024). This is especially true to those in medicine and law.

However, there are other factors that can contribute to this and they include: low self-esteem, low self-efficacy, lack of self-confidence, poor social support, maladaptive perfectionism, inadequate preparation

and poor time management (Jirjees, et al., 2024). Self-esteem and social support are two major variables that have been shown to influence examination anxiety. These two factors will be well expounded during the course of this study. Self-esteem refers how individuals perceive their own worth, capabilities, strengths and weaknesses. These notions or core beliefs about one self plays a critical role in how students respond to stress. Self-esteem is influenced by core beliefs about oneself that is formed from childhood through series of experiences (PositivePsychology.com, n.d). It is shaped by our perception of the world and how much of a role we believe to play in it and this is why emotional, physical and mental validation from our environment is deeply crucial. Self-esteem and examination anxiety have a complex relationship. Students with a high self-esteem are more likely to approach examinations with more confidence, composure and positivity, while those with low self-esteem may battle with feeling inadequate or fearful of failure. Conversely, high test anxiety can lead to a negative perception of one's abilities, creating a cycle of reduced confidence, pressure and stress.

Similarly, social support is the perception or reality that one is cared for or has support, guidance and assistance from friends, family or even significant others and this is known to cushion the effects and impacts of stress. According to Farmer and Farmer (1996), it is "the processes of social exchange that contribute to the development of individuals' behavioral patterns, social cognition and values." Students who feel regarded and supported are less likely to internalize academic pressure, academic failure which may significantly reduce their susceptibility to examination anxiety. Students attitude and behaviors towards academics is highly influenced by key social agents such as friends, family, classmates (Ines Blazevic, 2016), hence, perceived social support is positively associated to students' academic motivation and success. Due to the immense pressure that comes with medical sciences and law, students often face unique academic challenges which include weighty workloads, high expectations for success, limited free time, critical decision making and much more. These stressors can increase anxiety levels, making it crucial to study how self-esteem and social support systems can influence their exam anxiety. According to Karim and Lachmi (2024), understanding the dynamics of examination anxiety is necessary for developing essential intervention programmes that can enhance students' academic experiences and overall mental and emotional wellbeing. Comprehending the relationship between these factors and anxiety can help form interventions that are directed towards improving student mental wellbeing and ultimately, academic success.

Statement of the Problem

In spite of the increasing awareness of mental health problems in academic environments, examination anxiety still significantly affects students' academic performance and overall psychological health. For highly demanding programs like medicine and law, students are more prone to chronic stress, toxic competitive environment and immense pressure to perform. Yet, the association between social support, self-esteem and anxiety are not always acknowledged or utilized. The gap is especially significant for medicine and law students who often bear the double burden of academic expectations and the psychological, emotional weight of their careers (Ayodele et al, 2018)

There is an increasing body of research that explores this topic in general populations but there is limited research, focused specifically on medical and law students within the Nigerian context. The Nigerian educational system is marked by competitive style of grading, limited resources, learning infrastructure and inadequate mental health support. The Nigerian society also amplifies this with unrealistic societal expectations in relation to the systemic challenges in education. Yet, students are required to thrive and excellently succeed in such demanding academic environments despite these challenges. In high stake programs like law and medical sciences, they are even more pronounced, where students are trained for

professional excellence under such intense workloads and unrealistic societal standards. In a study by BK Yadav in 2023, the prevalence of anxiety among university students was found to be at 70.4% of which a significantly higher percentage was among medical students. Also, given the unique demands of law school: pressure to attain high class rankings, over-performance and land spots in law journals and schools, etc. An article written by Mike Robinson, explained that 96% of law students face significant stress, compares to 70% of medical students and 43% of graduate students.

It is hence concerning how little attention is paid to exactly how much this pressure has a psychological toll on students. Exam anxiety is not an uncommon experience, in fact it is the code by which students live by, devising ways to cope with this issue. Many students experience such academic burnout, physical symptoms and debilitating self-doubt. Whilst some students might possess the intellectual capacity to succeed academically, their mental state often undermines their ability to do so. It is not simply individualistic, but a reflection of an unhealthy educational culture that emphasizes outcomes over emotional and psychological support.

Self-esteem and psychological support are two significant variables that influence how students cope with academic stress. In the Nigerian university setting, students are often faced with factors that impede self-esteem such as hyper criticism, lack of encouragement and a grading system that equals self-worth to academic performance. Also, the culture of isolation, limited time to socialize, competition and fear of vulnerability often impedes levels of social support.

Hence, this study seeks to fill that gap by investigating and depicting how self-esteem and perceived social support relate to examination anxiety among these students. It explores how these two relatively modifiable psychological factors relate to examination anxiety amongst medical and law students. The aim is to then identify whether there is indeed a significant positive correlation between these psychological variables and to what extent. Understanding this relationship, would then expose ways to create student centered solutions and challenge the narrative that academic success should be at the expense of mental and emotional well-being. To achieve this, the study will also answer the following research questions:

1. Will Self Esteem significantly Predict exam anxiety among medical and law students?
2. Will Social support significantly predict Exam anxiety among medical and law students?
3. What is the relationship between self-esteem and social support among Medical and Law students and to what extent do they impact each other?

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to:

- i. Delve into the roles of self-esteem and perceived social support in influencing examination anxiety among medical and law students in Godfrey Okoye University. These disciplines in particular are known for their academic intensity, rigorous curriculum, immense workload, limited free time, high expectations and emotionally demanding environments. Students in these programs are faced with an immense pressure to succeed which can lead to heightened levels of anxiety especially during examinations.
- ii. This research will study how individual psychological factors (such as self-esteem) and social support systems interact to affect student's experiences of examination anxiety as well as identify if self-esteem and social support do serve as protective factors or predictors of examination anxiety.
- iii. The study will also explore whether there are differences in levels or experience of examination anxiety between medical and law students. The results of this study are then expected to aid the formation of

mental health interventions, academic counselling services and even institutional policies that would support students' academic performance and overall emotional well-being.

Literature Review

Theoretical Review

This study is based on six psychological theories that provide knowledge into the dynamics between self-esteem, social support and anxiety. These theories offer a foundation for understanding how environmental and interpersonal factors influence students' academic stress responses, particularly in high pressure academic programs such as medicine and law.

Self Esteem Theories

Self Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985)

This theory is the brainchild of two psychologists, Richard Ryan and Edward Deci and it posits that individuals are more likely to possess high self-esteem and develop a more stable and positive sense of self when they have certain psychological needs for autonomy, competence and connection to others met. Self-determination is our ability to make decisions for ourselves (Cloke, 2022). Students who feel competent in their academic abilities and can maintain control over their learning process could possess higher self-esteem.

Three basic psychological needs are highlighted; Autonomy, Competence and Relatedness which their inter-relatedness directly affects another key factor that could impact self-esteem and intrinsic motivation. In regards to autonomy, students can feel a sense of control over their learning experiences when given independence over tasks, setting their own goals and giving them opportunity to exercise their own initiative. When for example, final year Law students are allowed to choose their own project/ Thesis (after providing them with enough learning resources of course) this likely has a ripple effect on perceived self-efficacy and competence. Learners who have high levels of intrinsic motivation actively participate in these experiences for self-development and growth. It can be increased through various things such as the ecstasy of learning something different or new, the satisfaction of curiosity or the satisfaction of completing a task (Iftikhar, et al., 2023). Intrinsic motivation of students also depends in these levels of self-efficacy or confidence that comes from autonomy. Intrinsic motivation is linked to deeper learning, better memory and increased academic performance. Deci and Ryan in their study found a positive correlation between an individual's intrinsic motivation to engage in tasks and their self-perception of competence when completing it.

However, further studies show that feelings of competence alone are not enough to enhance intrinsic motivation unless accompanied by a sense of autonomy of highly internalized locus of causality. The theory invariably is positing that for students to develop self-esteem, they must be given tasks that reinforce autonomy and a healthy balance between dispositional and situational attributions. In high pressure programs like Medicine, where examinations like the Mbbs exams are major determinants of their career furtherance, students pass rates in a study over a 7year period saw a significant increase in performance (from 63.4% to 76.5%) when clinicians were hired as lecturers (Tochukwu, et al, 2013). This introduction improved teaching quality, leading students to feel more competent in the subject. This fits into the theory, as perceived competence strengthens intrinsic motivation and self-esteem which reduces anxiety.

The study also highlighted the need for relatedness as the introduction of clinicians provided social inclusion and emotional support, especially since they served as a source of inspiration. In essence, medical or law students feel connected to their academic environment as they are more likely to have a higher self-esteem, lower examination anxiety and more endurance and resilience under stress. It emphasizes the role of social support as well. Ryan and Deci (1985) suggest that our social conditions have a large tendency to influence

self-determination. Study groups are very helpful for courses like these with a hefty workload. Study groups for example, are a form of peer support and has the potential to enhance student life satisfaction. When students receive peer support and feel able to reciprocate, they tend to perceive higher levels of study engagement (Sanna, et al., 2024). Strong social connections amongst law students in law school for example, can foster motivation and improve well-being, reducing levels of examination anxiety. To alleviate examination tension, peer support needs to be cultivated, triggering students' sense of relatedness and study engagement.

Sociometer Theory (Leary, 2000)

Developed by Leary in 2000, the theory offers a valuable framework for understanding the role of self-esteem in academic functioning. The core of this theory posits that self-esteem can act as a social meter that monitors the extent to which we feel valued, accepted or included by others. Wikipedia describes that the self-esteem system acts as an aid to measure the quality of an individual's current interpersonal relationships. In regards to academic life, medical and law students may evaluate their self-worth based on how accepted or valued they feel by their peers, lecturers and family. High perceived social connection and support reinforces feelings of inclusion, thereby raising self-esteem and buffering against examination anxiety. Parallel to this notion, perceived rejection or lack of support may lower self-esteem and heighten vulnerability to academic stress. Self-esteem is not just an internalized notion of self-worth, but how we think or believe others see and value us, especially in evaluative settings like school.

According to this theory, self-esteem is then not just a personal trait or internal self-worth but mirrors and fluctuates in response to perceived social feedback. When students feel included, seen and respected, their sociometer registers a positive social standing, which leads to higher self-esteem. When individuals perceive exclusion or rejection, their self-esteem declines and the sociometer likely perceive that as a threat to sense of belonging. In academic environments where performance and evaluation are constant, this theory is particularly pronounced.

In the context of university students, especially those in high pressure faculties such as medicine and law, this theory becomes particularly relevant. Students' self-esteem anchors on how they perceive others' evaluations of their abilities, intelligence and performance. In such competitive environments, subtle form of exclusion, comparison or even perceived under performance can cause a drop in self-esteem. For example, a medical student who repeatedly sees their peers being selected for roles or given public recognition may begin to internalize feelings of inadequacy, even if their performance is objectively good. This perceived under performance, especially when surrounded by high achieving peers, can significantly lower their self-esteem and increase vulnerability to exam related anxiety. This example then supports this study by explaining how perceived social validation expressed through social support can influence a student's self-esteem and ultimately, examination anxiety. When students receive reliable, constant regard and support from peers, lecturers and family, it establishes their sense of being valued and accepted, raising their self-esteem and reducing likelihood of examination anxiety.

This theory conceptualizes two types of self-esteem; State Self-esteem and Trait self-esteem. State self-esteem refers to the current feelings one has about themselves in relation to situational events. It fluctuates in response to the events that happen around us. In other words, people's views of the extent to which they are or likely to be valued and accepted by other people in the present or near future. Trait self-esteem refers to an individual's average or typical level of self-esteem across time and varied situations. It explains their view of the degree to which they are generally valued and accepted by others. Periodic tests of abilities such as examinations can have an effect on state self-esteem. Passing an examination will likely increase levels

of self-esteem and reduce anxiety towards other examinations whilst failure would likely decrease levels of self-esteem whilst increasing levels of anxiety. However, an externally determined view of success and failure can play an influential role. This externally determined view involves the view of peers, family and friends. Social acceptance of a student who is faced with an exam, lessens feelings of anxiety, especially when such validation has been established over time. In other words, whether they fail or pass, so long as the perceived acceptance remains, it buffers and stabilizes levels of self-esteem.

Social Support Theories

Buffering theory (Cohen & Wills, 1985)

Perceived Social Support in this study refers to the extent to which one believes that they have assistance whether emotionally, mentally, spiritually or even financially from family members, friends, loved ones, etc. This theory according to Cohen and Willis, posits that social support serves as a protective factor that attenuates or “buffers” the adverse effects of stress on an individual’s psychological and physical wellbeing. According to this theory, it is simply the presence of social support that lessens mental stress but can become especially helpful when an individual is exposed to really high levels of stress and anxiety such as examination conditions. Invariably, the more social support an individual access, the more their mental and physical health improves (Bekiros, et al., 2022).

In academic settings, performance pressure, high unrealistic expectations, fear of failure all contribute to stress levels of students during examinations. The theory suggests that perceived social support serves a kind of absorbent shield that can significantly reduce the psychological impact of such stressors. It does this by reducing the intensity and responses to stress that would in turn prevent or reduce the development of negative results such as mental health problems, physical health problems and even maladaptive coping behaviors. Law and medical students often encounter chronic stressors such as intensive studying, complex study material, competitive environment and frequent difficult examinations such as the Bar examinations for Law Students and the MBBS examinations for medical students. These courses also require high and intensive focus that can sometimes lead to social isolation. These factors elevate their risk for examination anxiety and psychological distress. This theory explains that social support acts as a moderating variable that either increase and reduce the effects of these stressors. For example, law students who receive emotional and informational support from peers, mentors and family may experience lower levels of anxiety during examination periods. Medical students who also are met with beneficial instrumental support such as study resources and structured guidance may feel more competent and less anxious. Social support can also be linked to health because it alleviates stress appraisals or weakens the relation between stress and negative health outcomes (Cohen & Wills, 1985)

According to Cohen’s theory as expanded by Bekiros, Jahanshahi and Munoz-Pacheco in 2022, there are three types of support: emotional support, instrumental support, informational support and appraisal support. Emotional support: this includes expressions of compassion, love, trust, care and encouragement. The impact of emotional support on anxiety is very huge. It helps students cope with emotions that stem from the pressures of the academic environment. It equips students with the tools helpful to confront tough situations, emphasizing the practical place of social support in mitigating challenges. This for example can look like a Law student, Sarah, being constantly reassured of their efforts towards their studies. This consistent validation can be helpful in buffering low self-esteem in Sarah. Informational support: this can include informational support, valuable learning resources, career mentorship and guidance, providing valuable advice and feedback. For example, senior student sharing study strategies or a lecturer offering advice on managing stress. Instrumental support: this refers to practical, tangible assistance that helps with

a need such as financial assistance, help with transportation, etc. Appraisal support involves feedback and affirmation that helps individuals evaluate themselves of their decisions accurately. This helps to strengthen self-esteem and confidence. These various aspects of support as essential for medical and law students to be able to thrive in such high-pressure environments.

It is important to note that the effectiveness of these support depends on the fit between the support provided and the individual's need during stressful situations. This means that support is most potent when it directly addresses the kind of stress that the individual is facing. For example, when final year law students are facing financial hardship during their final year, instrumental support (such as monetary aid or provision) would be the most helpful. Ultimately, the theory emphasizes that not all support is equally effective in all situations. It is not a one size fits all which is one of the major criticisms of this theory. Mismatched or poorly delivered support can have negative or neutral effects.

Another criticism of this theory is that it tends to focus heavily on perceived support than actual support. What people believe they have versus what they actually have. Some scholars argue that what is more important is the actual availability and quality of support more than one's perception of it.

Attachment Theory (Bowlby, 1969)

The relationship between caregiver and infant during childhood has a major impact on how individuals relate to others throughout life. These early experiences lead to the development of internal working models which are mental representations of self and others and influence a person's ability to form, maintain and perceive relationships. This internal working models are of two types: model of self and model of others. This theory was expanded through the strange situation experiment by Mary Ainsworth in 1978 which identified secure, anxious and avoidant attachment styles in infants. These styles are merged into personality and persist even till adulthood and shaping how individuals approach relationships, seek support and cope with stress.

For students in academic and high stress environments such as law and medical school, attachment styles affect how they perceive social support, manage anxiety and maintain self-esteem. It offers a valuable lens for understanding individual differences in self-esteem, social support perception and examination anxiety. These dynamics are very relevant in environments where students coping strategies and interpersonal resources significantly impact their experience of examination anxiety (Wei, et al., 2007). According to John Bowlby, attachment styles refer to the patterns of expectations, needs and emotions one displays in interpersonal relationships, specially formed in childhood through interactions with caregivers.

Three styles of attachment are highlighted; Anxious attachment style, Avoidant attachment style and Secure attachment style. Anxious attachment styles are characterized by low self-esteem, a fear of rejection and abandonment. They tend to be overly needy due to a lack of self-esteem; this then crucially affects their ability to seek and accept social support. This could have resulted from an emotional inconsistency from caregivers as a child. It reinforces a feeling of fear and anxiety in interpersonal relationships. A student with an anxious attachment style may constantly fear failure and social rejection which leads to heightened self-criticism, low self-esteem, especially during strenuous examination seasons. Attachment styles also have a direct influence in our anxiety levels. Research explains that students with anxious attachment are more prone to developing anxiety disorders such as generalized anxiety disorder, social phobia and panic disorders. Students who perceive low social support due to their attachment style may experience increased examination anxiety.

Avoidant attachment styles are characterized by emotional distance, independence, discomfort with closeness usually stemming from inconsistency from caregivers which leads them to suppress needs and

desires for closeness. Students with this style often suppress their emotions, avoid relying on others for help or support and value self-reliance, sometimes to the point of isolation. They may appear confident or even emotionally detached but often have quite fragile self-esteem. Most often, their self-esteem is tied to achievements and self-control more than emotional connection, making academic hurdles feel like threats to their sense of being. It also has direct implications on perceived social support. Avoidant students are less likely support even when they need it. They may perceive help as intrusive, not trust others to be emotionally available and even in high pressure environments, may self-isolate believing that they can handle themselves which increases psychological strain. They may intensify academic stress by undermining the effective roles of self-worth and supportive relationships (Wei, et al., 2007). Despite calm exterior, avoidant individuals often experience high internal stress and examination anxiety but may suppress or even deny those feelings. Secure attachment styles develop from consistent, responsive care giving. People with this attachment style have emotional stability, healthy interdependence and a strong sense of self-worth. In academic environments, they are more likely to have high self-esteem and perceive available social support which is very key in alleviating exam anxiety. In terms of social support, securely attached students are comfortable seeking support under duress. They are also trustworthy and emotionally available, which increases their sense of social support. Securely attached students form healthy peer relationships and utilize these social connections that act as a buffer against academic pressure.

However, this theory is not without its criticisms. Firstly, its overemphasis on early interactions between infants and primary caregivers may overlook the impact of later life experiences such as peer relationships, academic challenges and even personal achievement that are of similar relevance. In the context of examination anxiety, academic environment and peer relationships play more immediate roles than experiences of childhood. Also, because bulk of research around this theory was done in Western context, it limits its applicability across various cultures. For example, behaviors seen as signs of secure and insecure attachment in one culture may not hold the same in other cultures. This bias then raises questions about the universality of these classifications and their relevance to students from different cultural backgrounds, such as those in Nigeria.

Test Anxiety Theories

Cognitive Appraisal Theory of Stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984)

This theory was developed by Richard Lazarus and he posits that stress is in its perception and interpretation rather than in the situations themselves. He explains that stress arises when there is a perceived imbalance between what is expected of a person and their ability to cope (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). He argues that stress is perceived by individuals differently based on their interpretations of the event and the outcome of a sequential pattern of thinking known as appraisals. Cognitive appraisals refer to the personal interpretation of an event that determines the extent to which the event is perceived as stressful. It involves identifying if a situation or event will negatively impact our wellbeing, whether there are sufficient resources at our disposal to cope with the demands of the circumstance and if our methods for dealing with these situations are feasible.

Appraisals are of two main types: Primary Appraisal and Secondary Appraisal. Primary Appraisal refers to the initial analysis of a situation to determine if it is potentially harmful, challenging or detrimental. It measures the extent to which a situation is relevant to one's goals and whether the encounter aligns with one's goals (Turner, et al., 2024). It involves assessing how the outcome of an event could affect oneself and this usually happens in fractions of seconds. Secondary Appraisal occurs right after when an individual assesses their available resources and options to cope with a challenge. Individuals then evaluate available

resources which include internal resources such as skills, knowledge and personal strengths as well as external resources including social support, financial resources and access to professional help. When a student perceives an exam as a threat to self-esteem, future opportunities or competence, they are more likely to experience intense anxiety. This anxiety in turn impairs concentration, memory and performance. This is especially true for students with low self-esteem or limited social support, who may doubt their ability to cope. Whilst students who perceive the examination as a task that they will be able to surmount, they are more confident, less anxious and are more likely to utilize adaptive coping strategies. Strong social support and healthy levels of self-esteem can reinforce the belief that they possess capability to handle such negative events.

A study by Toth et al. (2022) found that students cognitive appraisals of examination situations and their irrational beliefs such as perfectionism significantly affects their examination related emotions. Negative appraisal of events leads to worry, fear and helplessness and can contribute to examination anxiety. Positive appraisal boosts motivation and focus as well as reduce examination anxiety and enhance test performance. In the analysis of this theory, it is crucial to examine how cognitive appraisals affect our emotions and why then emotional responses varies per individual. It buttresses how emotions occur through a transactional appraisal method. According to this theory, emotions occur due to the interaction between the goals of the individual and how environmental encounters are represented. Emotions such as anxiety generate from a specific nature of appraisals. Anxiety is a future oriented emotion that has a core theme of uncertain threats such as failure of examinations. Academic examinations are then more likely to induce anxiety because they are crucial to student goals.

Furthermore, primary appraisals are then concerned with how relevant an encounter is to one's goals also known as goal relevance (GR) and whether such encounters are in alignment with one's goals known as (Goal Congruence). Secondary appraisal then reflects one's alternatives for coping with the encounter. It could either be problem focused coping or emotion focused coping. Problem focused coping involves evaluation of one's capacity to directly align the situation to one's goals whilst emotion focused coping involves ability to psychologically adapt to the situation whether by adjusting one's perception, desires or beliefs (Fortune, et al., 2024).

Appraisals are shaped by factors such as socio-cultural expectations. In the Nigerian academic system, where academic success is often linked to future opportunities or family pride, examinations are appraised within increased emotional importance. It intensifies primary appraisal as a threat and places more demand on internal (self-esteem) and external (social support) mechanisms. For example, a medical student who failed a previous examination may perceive an upcoming test as a threat to her self-esteem (primary appraisal) and if she also believes she lacks the academic skill or emotional resilience to cope (secondary appraisal), examination anxiety would likely increase. If she however receives social support from mentors of peers, she may reappraise the situation, buffering stress and reducing anxiety

Yerkes Dodson Law (Yerkes & Dodson, 1908)

A very important framework for understanding the relationship between stress and performance is the Yerkes Dodson Law, proposed by Yerkes and Dodson in 1908. It posits a curvilinear relationship between arousal and performance. The assumption of this principle explains that performance improves with an increase in arousal up to an optimal point and any further arousal leads to a performance decline. Invariably, this suggests that a moderate level of examination anxiety can motivate student and increase alertness, whilst excessive anxiety can impair concentration, memory and overall test performance. It is particularly very relevant to this study as it provides a structure for understanding how internal (self-esteem) and external

(social support) resources may buffer against the harmful effects of exam stress. Excessive Anxiety that stems from low self-worth or poor support systems may affect memory recall, cognitive functioning, and even impair concentration.

The Yerkes Dodson law can be linked to constructs in this study. Self-esteem reflects a student's sense of self-worth and confidence. Students with high self-esteem are more likely to view exams as challenges than as threats, placing them within the arousal zone. Conversely, low self-esteem may then predispose students to increased examination anxiety, pushing them over the over arousal zone. This is in alignment to the Cognitive Appraisal theory that states that perception of stress affects how a student deal with it. This evaluation then influences arousal level.

The same can be said for social support. Social support provides emotional, academic and psychological resources that buffer stress. When students feel supported by family, friends and peers, emotional regulation becomes a lot easier, especially with anxiety. This is explained through the Buffering Hypothesis (Cohen & Wills, 1985) which suggests that social support can protect individuals from the negative effects of stress. This provision of reassurance, encouragement and practical help, hence preventing anxiety from exceeding functional levels.

Law and Medicine Students face higher academic pressure, hence, making them more susceptible to high arousal, according to the Yorkes Dodson Law, especially when under poor support or low self-esteem. Inevitably, they operate close to the upper limits of the arousal performance curve. This Law is praised for its practical applicability across different contexts of performance, from academic testing to workplace productivity and even sports. Its diagrammatic illustration makes it both theoretical and practical for discussions. It also aligns well with empirical observations about examination anxiety that a moderate amount of anxiety can motivate study and focus whilst too much can have disadvantages.

It has also been criticized for a few limitations. Firstly, its over simplistic nature does not specify what "optimal arousal" means in measurable terms neither does it explain individual differences in stress tolerance. It also doesn't exemplify what type of task is involved. More research reveals that more complex cognitive tasks (like examinations in medicine and law) would then require lower optimal arousal than others. It also does not indepthly account for the influence of psychological variables such as social support and self-esteem. There is hence a need for more nuanced models that include emotional, cognitive and sociocultural influences.

Empirical Review

This section presents a review of empirical studies that study the relationships among self-esteem, social support and examination anxiety among university students. Emphasis is however placed on studies that involve students in high pressure academic environments such as medicine and law. Research has consistently revealed a negative correlation between self-esteem and anxiety among Nigerian undergraduates. In Lagos State University, a study found that higher self-esteem was associated with lower levels of depression and anxiety. Out of the 235 university students, 65.2% of participants experienced probable anxiety, highlighting its prevalence among students.

In a similar study at Rufus Giwa Polytechnic in Owo, it was discovered that 56% of its students had depression, 42% experienced anxiety and a whopping 53% exhibited low self-esteem. The study also found significant negative correlations between self-esteem and anxiety, suggesting that measures to boost self-esteem could reduce anxiety levels ($r = -0.687$) Another study at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria found that self-esteem positively correlated with academic performance ($r = 0.24$) while test anxiety had a negative

correlation ($r=-0.43$). In this study, although social support was not directly measured, these findings suggest that social support factors play a crucial role in academic success.

Similarly, another study in Ibadan examined self-esteem, locus of control and gender in relation to exam anxiety. Results indicated that self-esteem and locus of control had significant impact on exam anxiety levels. These findings hence suggest that enhancing psychological support systems that influence locus of control could buffer exam related stress. In specific context to medical and law students, there are recent studies to investigate the prevalence, causes and psychological correlates of examination anxiety among medical and law students. A cross sectional study conducted at Unaizah College of Medicine in Saudi Arabia assessed test anxiety among 222 medical students using the West side anxiety scale. The results showed high prevalence of test anxiety, with significant associations identified between exam anxiety and factors such as low self-esteem and lack of social support. Yet, it emphasized the need for educational interventions that address these psychological factors that address these psychosocial factors that alleviate test anxiety among medical students.

In a 2021 study on the mental wellbeing of law students, participants were assessed for anxiety, 38% of respondents reported at least one diagnosis of anxiety in their life, 22.5% of whom reported that they had been diagnosed since resuming in law school. The study also found that self-esteem significantly influenced student's ability to cope with exam stress. A cross-sectional study conducted at Mattu University in Ethiopia measured test anxiety among 421 science students. The study utilized the Westside Anxiety Scale, the Oslo social support scale and the Rosenberg self-esteem scale. Findings showed that lower self-esteem and inadequate social support were significant predictors of higher test anxiety levels.

Similarly, a study published by National Journal of Community Medicine investigated exam anxiety among Indian Medical Students. The results showed that students experiencing excessive course loads and psychological stress were more likely to report high levels of exam anxiety. The study emphasized the role of self-esteem in buffering against academic stressors and suggested that interventions aimed at improving self-esteem could be beneficial in reducing examination anxiety. It also suggests that interventions aimed at enhancing self-esteem could lead to improved academic results and reduced anxiety levels among law students.

For social support, Camacho et al. (2021) examined how social support influenced student motivation during the Covid-19 lockdown in Portugal. Their findings showed that anxiety significantly reduced motivation, while teacher support buffered this decline, whereas classmate support had no significant impact. In another study by Li, Ahmad and Roslan (2025) they investigated emotional support from parents, teachers, and friends among 565 Chinese final year high school students. They found that emotional support sources did not directly predict exam anxiety, but they had indirectly reduced anxiety via increased academic buoyancy, a resilience to setbacks.

Omaima Saleem et al. (2025) also examined 40 young adults using the West side Test Anxiety scale and MSPSS. Their findings showed that family support had a weak yet significant negative correlation with exam anxiety. While direct studies on social support's impact on examination anxiety among Nigerian Students are limited, related research underscores the importance of psychological factors in academic performance. While direct studies on social support's impact on examination anxiety among Nigerian Students are limited, related research underscores the importance of psychological factors in academic performance. It is however, important to note that specific research focus on Nigerian Medical and law students is scarce. Only few studies have simultaneously examined self-esteem and social support as predictors of examination anxiety, particularly among medical and law students.

In Contrast, research from the University of Uyo showed that although anxiety significantly impacted academic performance, self-esteem did not show a significant effect. It suggests that the influence of self-esteem on academic outcomes may vary across various contexts. However, studies have shown that students in high pressure academic environments such as medical and law program, often experience high levels of stress and anxiety, which subsequently underscores the need for targeted research in these populations to develop effective interventions.

While considerable research has been conducted on examination anxiety among university students, several critical gaps remain, particularly within high pressure disciplines such as medicine and law in Nigeria. A majority of the literature stems from western educational settings with very limited representation from Nigerian Universities. This lack of context specific data limits the existence and development of culturally responsive mental health strategies. Finally, much of the existing research relies solely on quantitative approaches, which while valuable, may not be able to capture the nuanced, lived experiences of students living with exam anxiety. Hence, this study aims to address these gaps by exploring the relationship between self-esteem and social support both independently and interactively on examination anxiety among medical and law students within Enugu State Nigeria.

Hypotheses

H1: Self-esteem will significantly predict exam anxiety among medical and law university students.

H2: Social support will significantly predict examination anxiety among Medical and Law university students.

H3: There would be a significant positive relationship between Self-esteem and social support among Medical and Law university students.

METHODOLOGY

This Study adopted a correlational survey research design. This design is suitable because it allows the researcher to explore the relationship between two psychological variables i.e. self-esteem, social support and examination anxiety, without manipulation. The goal was to determine the degree and direction of association of these variables as they naturally occur among university students in intense pressure academic environments such as Medicine and Law.

Participants

The participants of this study were undergraduate students from the faculty of law and college of Medicine at Godfrey Okoye University Enugu. A total of 120 students participated in this study. They combined both male and female students across academic levels ranging from 100-600 level. The Age range of participants was 16-25 years, reflecting the typical age bracket of undergraduate students in Nigeria Universities.

Technique

The sampling technique used in this study was a combination of stratified random sampling, purposive and convenience sampling techniques. Stratified random sampling was used to select Godfrey Okoye University as target sample. By dividing universities in Enugu that offer both medicine and law, the researcher created strata and then conducted a simple random sampling to arrive at the picked university. Purposive sampling was used to select participants from the faculties of law and medicine, due to the unique high demands and relevance of these faculties to the research focus of examination anxiety. Convenience sampling was then employed in distributing the questionnaire. The researcher approached students who were willing and readily available as well as met the inclusion criteria. Although this method might not guarantee full representation, it was appropriate given the specificity of research focus, and the need for voluntary participation

Instrument

Data was collected using a structured questionnaire composed of three standardized psychological scales.

1. The questionnaire included a section that obtained information on participant's age, gender, faculty and academic level.

Following approval, questionnaires were distributed digitally by the researcher using several social media platforms. Participants were assured of confidentiality and anonymity. They were also provided with a written informed consent. Completed form were then retrieved digitally

2. Rosenberg Self-esteem Scale

This was developed by Morris Rosenberg (1965), this is a 10 item likert type scale used to assess self-worth and image by measuring both positive and negative feelings about one self. Responses are rated from Strongly Agree to Strongly disagree. Higher scores indicate higher self-esteem.

Validity and Reliability

Demonstrates high reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.77-0.88$) and strong test-retest consistency ($r = 0.82-0.88$). Studies have further supported its construct validity and reliability across populations (Wongpakran & Wongpakaran, 2012). It is also valid across multiple cultures and population (Park & Park 2019)

Multidimensional scale of Social Support.

This was developed by Zimet, et al. (1988), the MPSS is a 12-item scale designed to measure perceived social support from three main sources: family, friends and significant others. Responses are rated on a 7-point Likert scale from strongly disagree to Strongly agree. Higher scores indicate higher degree of perceived social support. It consistently shows high internal consistency with Cronbach's alpha values ranging from 0.85 to 0.91(Wongkaparn, et al, 2019.) It is also validated across cultures, with a strong construct validity and factorial structure.

West side Test Anxiety Scale.

This was developed by Driscoll in 2007, the WTAS is a 10-item scale intended to access exam related anxiety in students. It comprises both emotional and cognitive symptoms of anxiety. Scoring is on a 5-point Likert Scale, scores are interpreted on a continuum from low to high anxiety.

Data Analyses and Results Presentation

Table 1: Means, Standard Deviations, and Correlations Among Study Variables

S/N	Variable	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	Age	1.35	0.51	–							
2	Gender	1.55	0.50	-.21*	–						
3	Positive Self-Esteem	15.20	2.50	.12	.08	–					
4	Negative Self-Esteem	10.80	3.00	.09	-.05	-.45***	–				
5	Family Support	19.80	4.20	.11	.04	.35**	-.28**	–			
6	Friends Support	20.60	3.80	.07	.06	.30**	-.25**	.52***	–		
7	Significant Other	18.90	4.60	.10	.03	.32**	-.22*	.48***	.54***	–	
8	Examination Anxiety	32.50	8.20	.24*	.02*	-.35***	.45***	-.25*	-.20*	-.30**	–

Age: 1 = 16-20, 2 = 21-25, 3 = 26+; Gender: 1 = Male, 2 = Female.

*** $p < .001$; ** $p < .01$; $p < .05$.

Correlation Findings:

Examination anxiety correlated positively with age ($r = .24, p < .05$), negative self-esteem ($r = .45, p < .001$), and negatively with positive self-esteem ($r = -.35, p < .001$), family support ($r = -.25, p < .05$), friends support ($r = -.20, p < .05$), and significant other support ($r = -.30, p < .01$).

Gender showed a weak but significant link to examination anxiety ($r = .02, p < .05$).

Self-esteem dimensions were strongly interrelated (positive vs. negative: $r = -.45, p < .001$). Social support dimensions also correlated positively (family/friends: $r = .52, p < .001$).

Table 2: Hierarchical Multiple Regression Predicting Examination Anxiety

Step	Predictors	R	R ²	ΔR ²	B	β (Beta)	T
1	Demographics	.24	.06	.06			
	Age				2.90	.14*	2.10*
	Gender				3.87	.19*	2.35*
2	Self-Esteem	.52	.27	.21			
	Positive Self-Esteem				-0.85	-.28***	-3.80***
	Negative Self-Esteem				1.20	.42***	5.20***
3	Social Support	.58	.34	.07			
	Family Support				-0.40	-.18*	-2.10*
	Friends Support				-0.15	-.07	-0.85
	Significant Other				-0.30	-.14	-1.65

*** $p < .001$; ** $p < .01$; $p < .05$.

B = Unstandardized Coefficient; β = Standardized Coefficient.

Regression Findings:

- Step 1 (Demographics):** Age ($\beta = .14, p < .05$) and gender ($\beta = .19, p < .05$) significantly predicted examination anxiety, explaining 6% of the variance.
- Step 2 (Self-Esteem):** Positive self-esteem ($\beta = -.28, p < .001$) and negative self-esteem ($\beta = .42, p < .001$) added 21% unique variance. Higher negative self-esteem increased anxiety; positive self-esteem reduced it.
- Step 3 (Social Support):** Only family support significantly predicted anxiety ($\beta = -.18, p < .05$), adding 7% variance. Friends and significant other support were non-significant.

Summary of Findings

- Age, gender, self-esteem (positive/negative), and social support (family/friends/significant other) correlated significantly with examination anxiety.
- Age and gender independently predicted examination anxiety.
- Self-esteem was the strongest predictor:
- Negative self-esteem increased examination anxiety.
- Positive self-esteem decreased examination anxiety.
- Social support (specifically family support) reduced examination anxiety, while friends and significant other support showed non-significant effects.
- The final model explained 34% of the variance in examination anxiety ($R^2 = .34$).

Self-esteem (particularly negative self-esteem) and family support are critical factors in examination anxiety among medical and law students. Interventions targeting self-esteem enhancement and family support systems may mitigate anxiety.

Discussion

This study critically analyzed the role of self-esteem and social support in predicting examination anxiety among medical and law students. The first hypothesis stated that there would be significant relationship between self-esteem and examination anxiety. The findings showed that the first hypothesis was indeed supported. Cor-relational analysis showed a significant negative relationship between positive self-esteem and examination anxiety but a significant positive relationship between negative self-esteem and examination anxiety. This suggests that students with low self-worth experience higher anxiety, while those with more positive self-beliefs had lower levels of anxiety during exams. It is also in line with the self-determination theory (Deci and Ryan, 1985) which attaches positive self-notions to psychological wellbeing. As well as the sociometer theory (Leary and Baumister, 2000), which emphasizes self-esteem as a reflection of social acceptance and value.

The second hypothesis was only partially supported. Correlational analysis revealed that all forms of social support (family, friends and significant other) had significant negative relationships with examination anxiety. Family support remained a very significant predictor of exam anxiety in the regression model. This indicates that students with higher perceived social support tend to report lower anxiety and the source and quality of such support is imperative. Family supports then appears to play a stronger buffering role in comparison to other forms of social support, which aligns with the Buffering hypothesis (Cohen and Willis, 1985)

The hierarchical regression analysis revealed that the third hypothesis, was strongly supported. When self-esteem was added in step 2, it suggests that an additional 21% of the variance in examination anxiety. Negative self-esteem was a strong positive predictor, while positive self-esteem was a strong negative predictor. This shows that self-esteem is not just related to exam anxiety, but a big predictor of it. The findings then reinforce the pivotal place of self-worth in emotional and mental responses to academic stressors.

Finally, the fourth hypothesis was partially supported as well. In the final step of the regression model, it is shown that only family support significantly predicted lower exam anxiety, whilst friends' support and significant other support did not contribute significantly to the prediction. The regression analysis indicated that not all types of support can significantly predict anxiety. It hence supports the attachment theory (Bowlby, 1969), which highlights the role of early secure attachments within the family in developing emotional and cognitive resilience.

Conclusion

This study delved into the role of self-esteem and social support in exam anxiety among medical and law students. The findings reveal that psychological and interpersonal resources significantly influence students' experiences of academic stress. According to the analysis, negative self-esteem significantly increased examination anxiety, while positive self-esteem reduced it. Amongst the types of social support, only family support significantly predicted lower anxiety levels. Age and gender had small but significant effects, with older students and females reporting higher anxiety. The model explained 34% of the variance in examination anxiety, with self-esteem as the strongest predictor. In essence, these discoveries highlight the importance of building self-worth and strengthening family-based support systems to significantly reduce academic stress in high pressure disciplines.

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